

Participation in informal learning contexts, self-perception of lifelong learning, and the digital participation of older adults

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Abstract

Digital participation is increasingly important for social inclusion, yet a considerable proportion of older adults remains offline. The present study investigates the role of informal learning contexts and the self-perception of lifelong learning for (the lack of) digital participation of older adults.

Drawing on four waves (2014, 2017, 2021, 2023) of the German Ageing Survey (DEAS), we analyze both the frequency of internet usage across different purpose groups (social, service, informal learning) in cross-sectional analyses and transitions from non-usage to usage and the reverse transition in longitudinal analyses.

The cross-sectional results reveal no single informal learning context that consistently predicts internet usage across all waves and purposes. The only exception is being culturally active, which is positively associated with the frequency of internet usage for all purposes in all waves. The self-perception of lifelong learning shows more stable positive associations with internet usage, particularly for service purposes.

In the longitudinal analyses, inter-individual differences in the frequency of participating in several informal learning contexts predict both the transition from non-usage to usage and from usage to non-usage, suggesting an association with openness to change rather than a directional effect. Intra-individual changes in informal learning contexts do not predict transitions, whereas an intra-individual improvement in the self-perception of lifelong learning increases the likelihood of transitioning from non-usage to usage.

Our findings suggest that a lifelong participation in informal learning contexts and a positive attitude towards learning need to be fostered as early as possible in adult life to support digital participation in older age.

Keywords: internet usage, onliners, offliners, attitudes towards learning, DEAS, hybrid panel analysis

Informal learning and digital participation for older adults

Since digitization is vastly evolving and permeates all aspects of society, not being able to take part in the digital world comes along with potential exclusion from many important aspects of daily life. For instance, digital participation includes a better access to information, social connections, healthcare services, and so forth (Ehlers et al., 2020; Wanka et al., 2023). Thus, having access to and using the internet, i.e., digital participation, is an important precondition for social participation (Koukiadis, 2025; Seifert et al., 2018). As the risk of social isolation rises with age (Huxhold & Engstler, 2019), accessing and using the internet might be an important factor to reduce the risk of social exclusion of older adults.

However, even though the share of older adults who use the internet and digital devices has been rising (Hunsaker & Hargittai, 2018), there is still a considerable proportion of older adults for whom this does not apply (Reissmann et al., 2023; Rennoch et al., 2024). Specifically, in 2020-2021, only 37% of the German 80+ population had been using the internet within the last 12 months (Reissmann et al., 2023). With respect to the younger older adults, another study indicated that 83% of the German population aged 61 to 75 had access to the internet in 2017 and 92% had access in 2020 (Kortmann et al., 2021). Even though these prevalences imply an improved digital participation, it should be noted that having access to the internet can only partially estimate the actual usage of internet. Moreover, access to the internet decreases for the age group ranging from 76 to 90 drastically, since only 45% of this age group had access to the internet in 2017 and 52% in 2020. Consequently, to support digital participation of older adults, it is important to identify factors that are beneficiary for internet use of older adults.

Informal learning contexts might be an important opportunity to gain knowledge about digital applications and to foster the entry into internet usage. Informal learning occurs in various daily situations beyond systematic or organized educational settings (Jin et al., 2019; Lima Flauzino et al., 2022; Villar & Celdrán, 2013). It is discussed to be the most important mode of learning for older adults compared to the other two modes of lifelong learning, i.e., formal and non-formal learning (Jin et al., 2019; Lima Flauzino et al., 2022; Villar & Celdrán, 2013). By participating in social or cultural activities, or interacting with family or friends, older adults might gain knowledge of or insight into what the internet has to offer incidentally, eliciting interest in using it. Since lack of interest in internet usage was the most important reason for 63% of older adults not to use the internet compared to costs (3%) or access (5%) (Helsper & Reisdorf, 2013), informal learning contexts might be an important trigger for becoming an internet user.

So far, studies have shown that internet usage in older adults is predicted by various individual factors: Men are more likely to use the internet than women, however the gender gap seems to shift as some recent studies cannot confirm it, which is interpreted as a potential closure of this gap for the young-old (Bünning et al., 2023; Hunsaker &

Hargittai, 2018). Moreover, age, socio-economic status, education, as well as health are positively related to internet use (Hunsaker & Hargittai, 2018; König et al., 2018; Rennoch et al., 2024). Rennoch et al. (2024) investigated the role of social contexts for internet use in adults older than 80 years. Participating in social activities was the only significant predictor for internet use when controlling for individual characteristics. This hints to the role social activities might play for becoming an internet user. However, the study by Rennoch et al. (2024) is cross-sectional and it is yet unclear what longitudinal effects can be observed when investigating the role of informal learning contexts for internet use. Moreover, since the potential purposes of internet use become more diverse with ongoing digitization and individuals might complement or compensate what they do offline with their online activities (Bünning et al., 2023), it might not be enough to differentiate between non-usage and usage of the internet. Instead, it seems necessary to additionally investigate the role of informal learning for different purposes of internet use such as staying in touch with one's social network or using services e.g., online banking to gain deeper insight into factors that facilitate internet use.

The present study

Against this background, the current study addresses the question of the role of informal learning contexts and the self-perception of lifelong learning for digital participation of older adults. Informal learning contexts are complemented by the self-perception of lifelong learning in the present study since an individual's answer to this construct might be based on their inference from observations of their own overt behavior (Bem, 1972). It thus functions as corrective for the operationalization of informal learning contexts and we assume that both can be predictive of internet use.

In a first step, we are interested in exploring the relation of informal learning contexts, self-perception of lifelong learning and frequency of internet use and how this is modulated by purposes of use, and specific types of informal learning contexts. We address this exploratory question with a cross-sectional analysis.

In a second step we are interested in whether these informal learning contexts or the self-perception of lifelong learning are associated with the transition from non-usage to usage of the internet, or the reverse transition of usage to non-usage of the internet. We address this question with a longitudinal analysis.

Our hypotheses are as follows:

H 1.1 The more frequent the participation in informal learning contexts, the more frequent the internet usage.

H 1.2 The more positive the self-perception of lifelong learning, the more frequent the internet usage.

H 2.1 The more frequent the participation in informal learning contexts (becomes) the more likely the transition from non-usage to usage of the internet.

H 2.2 The more positive the self-perception of lifelong learning (becomes) the more likely the transition from non-usage to usage of the internet.

H 3.1 The less frequent the participation in informal learning contexts (becomes) the more likely the transition from usage to non-usage of the internet.

H 3.2 The more negative the self-perception of lifelong learning (becomes) the more likely the transition from usage to non-usage of the internet.

Methods

Data

The paper is based on the German Ageing Survey (DEAS) which is a representative panel study focused on the second half of life, i.e., 40 years and older (Klaus et al., 2017). The data are conducted with a face-to-face or telephone interview which is followed by an additional questionnaire (drop-off) on paper or online.

For the analysis, we use the four waves (2014, 2017, 2021, 2023) of the DEAS, in which digital participation is conducted. For the sampling we focus on adults who were aged 65 and older. This means that we only analyze information from interviews, in which the respondents were at least 65 years old *during* the interview, regardless of their age in their first interview or their age in 2014. Additionally, we exclude respondents who did not answer the additional questionnaire and who had missing values on the dependent, independent or the control variables. For the longitudinal sample we only keep respondents who participated in at least two panel waves (see table 1).

The cross-sectional sample consists of 6,424 respondents for 2014, of 2,960 respondents for 2017, of 2,645 respondents for 2021, and of 2,179 respondents for 2023 (see table 2).

For the longitudinal sample four trajectories were identified: transition from non-usage to usage (1), transition from usage to non-usage (2), stable internet usage (3) and stable non-usage (4). Two transitions were analyzed (see analytical strategy). Both respective analytical samples include trajectories with constant usage (3 & 4). The first analytical sample additionally contains the trajectory with the transition from non-usage to usage (1) and consists of 3,249 respondents with 9,175 observations. The second analytical sample includes the trajectory with the transition from usage to non-usage (2) and consists of 3,107 respondents with 8,705 observations (see table 3).

Measures

The dependent variables stem from the additional questionnaire and contain information on the frequency of internet usage for different purpose groups, after asking whether

participants have access to the internet. For the cross-sectional analysis, we categorized the frequencies into three categories (“non-usage”, “occasional usage”, “frequent usage”, see figure 1). Here, we investigate the effect of the explanatory variables for four dependent variables, the first variable covers *all* purposes of internet usage, the second covers *social* purposes, the third *service* purposes and the fourth *informal learning* purposes (see figure 1 for the categorization of frequencies and purposes). For the longitudinal part, the frequency of internet usage is dichotomized to analyze transitions. For this purpose, the categories “occasional usage” and “frequent usage” are summarized as “usage”. Two dependent variables are looked at: The transition from usage to non-usage and the transition from non-usage to usage.

The first explanatory variable measures the self-perception of lifelong learning and is part of the AgeCog-scale (Diehl et al., 2021; Steverink et al., 2001). It contains the agreement on a four-point scale (strongly agree to strongly disagree) to the statement “Ageing means to me that I can still learn new things”.

Further explanatory variables are the frequency of participation in nine informal learning contexts, and we grouped the frequency into three categories (“never”, “occasionally”, “frequently”). The contexts are going for a walk, doing sport, being artistically active, being culturally active, attending sporting events, playing board games, attending courses, meeting a stable group of people and attending gatherings (see figure 2 for categorization and all questions). When analyzing the different purposes of internet use as dependent variable, the internet use for the other two purposes is added as explanatory variables.

We control all models for gender, vocational education, chronological age, having ever participated in the labor market, existence of grandchildren, existence of children, network size and subjective health.

In the cross-sectional part we use the integrated weights for the drop-off sample (FDZ-DZA, 2023).

Analytical Strategy

The analysis is separated into a cross-sectional and a longitudinal part.

First, we use multivariate weighted least squares regressions for each panel wave and for the different purpose groups (Cameron & Trivedi, 2010). With this strategy, we analyze the relation between frequency of internet usage and both, the self-perception of lifelong learning and the participation in informal learning contexts, over time and across different purpose groups.

Then, we use logistic hybrid panel regression models to analyze transitions from non-usage to usage of the internet (1) and the reverse transition from usage to non-usage (2). With this part of the analysis, we focus on how the occurrence of these transitions is associated with both inter-individual differences between older adults and intra-

individual developments in informal learning (Brüderl, 2010; Rabe-Hesketh & Skrondal, 2008; Wooldridge, 2009). The coefficients are displayed as average marginal effects (AME) following Mood (2010).

Results

Relation between internet usage and self-perception of lifelong learning and informal learning contexts – Cross-sectional part

When looking at all purposes descriptively, there are about 33% non-users in 2014, 34% in 2017, 21% in 2021 and 15% in 2023 in our sample. About 15% in 2014, 13% in 2017, 9% in 2021 and 8% in 2023 use the internet occasionally. The frequent users are the largest group in every wave, as they are about 52% in 2014, 53% in 2017, 70% in 2021 and 77% in 2023 (see table 4 also for socioeconomic descriptives and figure 3 for social, service and informal learning purposes).

The results for the association of the participation in informal learning contexts and the self-perception of lifelong learning with the frequency of internet usage can be found in table 5 and figure 4 for all purposes, in table 6 and figure 5 for social purposes, in table 7 and figure 6 for service purposes and in table 8 and figure 7 for informal learning purposes.

Attending gatherings is significantly and positively associated with the frequency of internet usage for all purposes in 2017 and 2023, but not in the other two waves. However, it does not predict internet usage when differentiating for different purposes of internet use.

Going for a walk does not predict the frequency of internet usage.

Doing sport is positively predictive of internet usage for all purposes in 2014, for social purposes in 2023, and for informal learning purposes in 2014.

Being artistically active is positively associated with all purposes of internet use in 2014 and 2021 and for social purposes in 2014. Contrarily, it is negatively associated with internet usage for all purposes in 2023. Being artistically active has no significant effect on internet usage for service and for informal learning purposes.

Being culturally active has a positive and significant effect in all waves when looking into all purposes of internet use. This is the only context with stable effects over all four waves. However, in the detailed analysis for purpose groups, the stability of the effect vanishes: being culturally active is positively predictive for social purposes only in 2023 and for informal learning purposes in 2014 and 2021. Yet, it is negatively predictive for service purposes in 2023 and for informal learning purposes in 2023.

Attending sporting events shows a negative significant effect on internet usage for all purposes in 2021 and for informal learning purposes in 2014. This context also shows a

positive significant effect for social purposes in 2017. It is not predictive for service purposes.

Playing board games shows a positive and significant effect for all purposes in 2021. This context does not predict internet usage for social, for service, or for informal learning purposes.

Visiting courses is positively and significantly associated with internet usage for all and for social purposes in 2014 and for service purposes in 2021. For the other waves and purposes, visiting courses does not predict the frequency of internet usage.

Meeting with a stable group of people has a positive and significant effect on internet usage only in 2021 for all purposes, social and service purposes. It is not related to internet usage in any of the other waves nor the internet use for informal learning purposes. Thus, except for informal learning purposes, meeting with a stable group of people is predictive of internet usage in 2021, which might be linked to the COVID-19 pandemic and its contact restrictions.

Not surprisingly, the strongest predictor for internet usage in one group of purposes is the usage of internet for other purpose groups. These are the highest and most stable effects over all four waves (see figures 5-7 and tables 6-8). There are, however, differences in how intensely the purposes are associated with one another. The usage of the internet for social purposes is more strongly related to the usage for informal learning purposes than to the usage for service purposes (see table 6 or figure 5). The usage of the internet for service purposes is also more closely related to the usage for informal learning purposes than to the usage for social purposes (see table 7 or figure 6). Finally, the usage for informal learning purposes is less strongly related to the usage for service purposes than to the usage for social purposes (see table 8 or figure 7).

Overall, we find contradictory evidence for the association of the frequency of participation in informal learning contexts with the frequency of internet usage. Even though there are some exceptions, in which there is a significant negative association of frequency of participation in informal learning contexts and frequency of internet use, we find more significant positive associations of frequency of participation in informal learning contexts and frequency of internet use across all purpose groups and waves. Hypothesis 1.1 thus is very dependent on the specific informal learning context and purpose of internet use. With respect to taking part in cultural activities, we can conclude that a more frequent participation in cultural activities is associated with a higher frequency of internet use for all purposes, supporting hypothesis 1.1. This cannot be concluded as clearly for other informal learning contexts.

For the relation between the frequency of internet usage for all purposes and the self-perception of lifelong learning, we find positive and significant effects, except in 2023. For social purposes, the self-perception of lifelong learning does not significantly predict

internet usage. For service purposes, we find a stable positive and significant effect of the self-perception of lifelong learning on usage of the internet for these purposes. For informal learning purposes, the self-perception of lifelong learning positively and significantly predicts usage in 2014 and 2017, but not in 2021 and 2023. Hypothesis 1.2 can thus be partly confirmed as the more positive the self-perception of lifelong learning, the more frequent the internet usage in part of the analyses.

Generally looking into all purposes seems to be more sensitive to the participation in informal learning contexts for internet usage than the analysis of detailed purpose groups. Therefore, we focus on transitions in internet usage for all purposes. i.e., we do not differentiate between purpose groups in the longitudinal part of our analysis.

Transitions from non-usage to usage and from usage to non-usage of the internet – Longitudinal part

In the longitudinal sample there are four types of trajectories (see table 9, also for socioeconomic descriptives): trajectories with the transition from non-usage to usage ($n = 247$, 7.4%), trajectories with the transition from usage to non-usage ($n = 104$, 3.1%), trajectories with stable usage of the internet ($n = 2,195$, 65.4%) and trajectories with stable non-usage of the internet ($n = 812$, 24.2%).

The results of the logistic hybrid panel regressions can be found in table 10.

In the between-results we find mostly positive significant effects of participating in informal learning contexts for the likelihood of starting using the internet. In more detail we found that older adults who attend gatherings, go for walks, do sport, are culturally active, play board games and visit courses more frequently are significantly more likely to transition from non-usage to usage. Still, we also find one negative significant effect: Older adults who attend sporting events less frequently are significantly more likely to transition from non-usage to usage. Inter-individual differences in the frequency of being artistically active and of meeting a stable group of people do not predict the likelihood of the transition from non-usage to usage. Overall, these results confirm hypothesis 2.1 with respect to inter-individual differences since the transition from non-usage to usage is more likely the more frequent one participates in informal learning contexts, even though we find a reverse effect for attending sporting events.

With respect to the self-perception of lifelong learning, the between-results of the hybrid panel regression show that older adults with a more positive self-perception of lifelong learning are significantly more likely to transition from non-usage to usage of the internet and thus confirm hypothesis 2.2 with respect to inter-individual differences.

The between-results for the control variables indicate, that women, grandparents and older adults are significantly less likely to transition from non-usage to usage, whereas a higher vocational education, the existence of children and a higher network size make the

transitions significantly more likely. Subjective health does not predict the likelihood for the transition.

Looking at the within-results, there are only two significant associations. Aside from the negative effect of the control variable of existence of grandchildren, which indicates that becoming a grandparent decreases the probability of transitioning from non-usage to usage, the only other significant within-effect is for intra-individual changes in the self-perception of lifelong learning. This effect indicates that if the self-perception of lifelong learning becomes more positive, the transition from non-usage to usage is more likely. Changes in the frequency of participation in informal learning contexts are not associated with the likelihood for the transition from non-usage to usage. Accordingly for intra-individual development hypothesis 2.1 must be rejected whereas hypothesis 2.2 can be confirmed.

For the transition from usage to non-usage of the internet the between results are similar to the results for the reverse transition. Regarding the effect of inter-individual differences on the likelihood to stop using the internet, we find mostly positive and one negative significant effect. The results show that older adults who attend gatherings, go for walks, do sports, are culturally active, play board games and visit courses more frequently are significantly more likely to transition from usage to non-usage. However, older adults who attend sporting events less frequently are significantly more likely to transition from usage to non-usage. Inter-individual differences in the frequency of being artistically active and of meeting a stable group of people is not associated with the likelihood of the transition from usage to non-usage. Therefore, hypothesis 3.1 must be rejected with respect to inter-individual differences in the overall picture, even though it can be confirmed for the context of attending sporting events.

Regarding the self-perception we find that older adults with a more positive self-perception of lifelong learning are significantly more likely to transition from usage to non-usage. This result is contrary to hypothesis 3.2 regarding the inter-individual differences, which thus must be rejected.

The control variables in the models analyzing the inter-individual differences in the transition from usage to non-usage are analogous to the between-effects for the reverse transition.

For the transition from usage to non-usage, none of the within-effects are significant. Therefore, changes in the participation in informal learning contexts and changes in the self-perception of lifelong learning do not predict the transition from usage to non-usage of the internet. Accordingly, both hypotheses (3.1 and 3.2) cannot be confirmed with respect to intra-individual developments based on the results.

Discussion

The present study investigates the role of informal learning contexts and the self-perception of lifelong learning for digital participation by analyzing frequencies of internet usage for different purposes over time in cross-sectional analyses and transitions both from non-usage to usage as well as from usage to non-usage in longitudinal analyses.

With respect to the informal learning contexts the exploratory cross-sectional analyses revealed that no specific learning contexts are predictive of frequency of internet use since there was much variability across purposes and waves. The only exception was that being culturally active is predictive of internet usage for all purposes taken together in all waves. Apart from this finding, the association of informal learning contexts with frequency of internet usage for the different purpose groups across the different waves changes a lot in an unsystematic way. Thus, the analysis reveals no clear pattern. But generally speaking, we observe positive associations more often than negative associations between frequency of internet usage and informal learning contexts. This pattern is in accordance with a previous study by Rennoch et al. (2024), in which social activities, composed of 14 leisure-time activities similar to our informal learning contexts, were significantly positively associated with internet use. Yet, the authors used the sum of activities that participants pursued as a measure and did not differentiate between different types of leisure activities (see Näsi et al., 2012 for a similar approach and comparable results). Thus, except for being culturally active, there does not seem to be a certain informal learning context that is specifically associated with the frequency of internet use. Rather the fact that one participates in multiple informal learning contexts seems to be associated with internet use as implied by Rennoch et al. (2024) and Näsi et al. (2012). Schehl et al. (2019) investigated the association of participating in cultural activities and different purposes of internet use, and found positive associations with all except for one online activity. We cannot replicate these findings, since being culturally active is only a stable (i.e., across all waves) significant predictor of the frequency of internet usage for all purposes taken together but not for single purpose groups. What remains unanswered in our and the above mentioned studies is whether the positive association of participation in social or cultural activities is only summative (i.e., the number of different activities older adults take part in predicts internet usage as shown in Näsi et al., 2012, Rennoch et al., 2024, and Schehl et al., 2019), or whether frequency of taking part in these activities is also important. Future investigations will have to clarify this.

Previous studies looking at the role of social or cultural activities for internet usage employed cross-sectional analyses (Näsi et al., 2012; Rennoch et al., 2024; Schehl et al., 2019). In the present study, we added a longitudinal approach to investigate whether these activities, that we conceptualize as informal learning contexts, are predictive of the transition from non-usage to usage of the internet or for the reverse transition, from usage to non-usage of the internet. Interestingly, the results imply that a higher frequency in

several informal learning contexts increases the likelihood of transitions – both from non-usage to usage, and from usage to non-usage of the internet. While in the cross-sectional results only one informal learning context, i.e., being culturally active, was predictive of the frequency of internet usage across all investigated waves, in the longitudinal results several informal learning contexts are predictive of the two transitions. However, this pattern can only be observed for inter-individual differences. With respect to intra-individual developments, i.e., changes within one respondent, none of the informal learning contexts are significant predictors of either of the transitions. This finding implies that to promote transitions into internet usage it might not be enough to support older adults to increase their participation in informal learning contexts. Instead, an earlier and lifelong participation in informal learning contexts, which needs to be fostered as early as possible in adult life, seems to be supportive.

The fact that both transitions, non-usage to usage and usage to non-usage, are predicted by a higher frequency of participation in a number of informal learning contexts allows for the interpretation that participating in informal learning contexts is rather associated with openness to change and not so much with the direction of the transitions of internet usage. This pattern is reinforced by the fact that self-perception of lifelong learning is also positively associated with both transitions in our longitudinal results. These findings are in accordance with a previous study on Dutch older adults looking at predictors of starting and stopping to use the internet (Berner et al., 2019). Similar to our results, they found analogous significant predictors (being younger and having a higher education) for both, starting and stopping the internet use. Berner et al. (2019) explain their findings with younger and higher educated adults being more exposed to the internet, thus more likely to use the internet, and consequently also the first to stop using the internet. In future investigations, personality traits could be included as control variables to investigate whether there are other reasons that might explain the general likelihood of transitions (see however Berner et al., 2013 for non-significant associations of changes in internet usage and openness or extraversion).

Self-perception of lifelong learning shows slightly more stable effects in the cross-sectional results than the informal learning contexts. This is in accordance with previous studies finding positive associations of internet usage and self-perception of aging (Mariano et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2026) or sense of mastery (Berner et al., 2019). Self-perception of lifelong learning in the present study is especially predictive for using the internet for service purposes and for all purposes taken together, less predictive for using the internet for informal learning purposes and not predictive for using the internet for social purposes. This could be interpreted as an indicator that the attitude towards learning is more important for service purposes than for the other purposes. With respect to social purposes this might imply that internet usage for this purpose is not so much associated with efforts of learning but is driven by other factors, e.g., the desire to stay in touch with family or friends. In the longitudinal results, we find that a more positive self-

perception of lifelong learning is predictive of both transitions. With respect to intra-individual developments the self-perception of lifelong learning is only predictive of the transition from non-usage to usage of the internet, which is expected and in accordance with previous findings (Wang et al., 2026).

We observe two unexpected findings with respect to the control variables. Firstly, subjective health was neither predictive of frequency of internet usage, nor of transitions in internet usage. This is in accordance with the finding of Berner et al. (2019). Yet, it is surprising against the background of previous studies showing that internet usage is predicted by cognitive functioning (Berner et al., 2015) or self-reported health (see Hunsaker & Hargittai, 2018 for a review; König et al., 2018). Secondly, becoming a grandparent makes it less likely to transition from non-usage to usage (the existence of grandchildren was not a significant predictor of internet use in the cross-sectional analysis by Rennoch et al., 2024). This could imply that becoming a grandparent comes along with additional requirements that might be so captivating that there is no capacity for another change. Yet, we did not control for the frequency of contact or closeness to family members or for whether grandparents take care of their grandchildren regularly. These aspects most likely also play an important role for transitions in internet usage and could be analyzed in future investigations. Other typical control variables such as age, vocational education or gender, previous effects could in most analyses be replicated in the present study (see Hunsaker & Hargittai, 2018 for a review).

We followed an explorative approach to study the role of informal learning contexts for digital participation of older adults. Due to the diverse nature of informal learning contexts there are numerous independent variables that might have lead to an overfitting of the data. Moreover, due to the number of hypotheses included in our study we ran many analyses which might have led to an alpha-inflation – this specifically concerns the different purposes of internet usage in the cross-sectional analyses. Despite these limitations, the present study gives a first insight into the role of informal learning contexts for the digital participation of older adults.

Conclusion

The results of the present study indicate that informal learning contexts and the self-perception of lifelong learning play a role in predicting the frequency of internet usage and the transitions in internet usage. We could not identify one specific learning context that plays a pivotal role for the frequency of internet usage. We rather find that different informal contexts are important for different purposes of internet usage at different points in time. The only exception is being culturally active, which is predictive of the frequency of using the internet for all purposes taken together across all waves. However, transitions of non-usage to usage and of usage to non-usage are predicted by the frequency of participating in several informal learning contexts. At the same time, intra-individual changes in participating in informal learning contexts in older age do not

predict transitions. Self-perception of lifelong learning tends to be positively related with the frequency of internet usage and an improvement in this self-perception even in older age increases the likelihood to transition from non-usage to usage of the internet. Still, the precise effects and mechanisms connecting internet usage with both informal learning contexts and self-perceptions towards learning need to be understood better.

To conclude, our results imply that a lifelong participation in informal learning contexts and a positive attitude towards learning are supportive for transitions into internet usage and thus need to be fostered as early as possible in adult life. Moreover, the cross-sectional analyses clearly show that using the internet for some purposes increases the probability of using it for other purposes. Thus, once an entry into internet usage is achieved for some purpose, it is easier to start using the internet for other purposes, too. This highlights the importance of taking the first step into the digital world and becoming increasingly included in older age, both digitally and socially.

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Data Availability Statement

The data underlying this article were provided by the German Centre of Gerontology (DZA) by permission. The data can be requested via the following link:

<https://www.dza.de/en/research/fdz/german-ageing-survey/access-to-deas-data>.

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Supplementary material

Figures

Figure 1. Measure for internet usage

Figure 2. Measure for informal learning contexts

Figure 3. Proportions of internet usage for purpose groups (in %, Data: DEAS 2014-2023)

Figure 4. Internet usage over time for all purposes (Data: DEAS 2014-2023)

Figure 5. Internet usage over time for social purposes (Data: DEAS 2014-2023)

Figure 6. Internet usage over time for service purposes (Data: DEAS 2014-2023)

Figure 7. Internet usage over time for informal learning purposes (Data: DEAS 2014-2023)

Tables

Table 1. Sampling

	Deleted	Retained
Initial DEAS sample (all waves, 1996-2023)		21,763
Not surveyed in 2014, 2017, 2021, and 2023 or younger than 65 during interview	10,596	11,167
Drop-off questionnaire not answered/completed	2,486	8,681
Missings on dependent variable	129	8,552
Missings on independent variables	180	8,372
Missings on control variables	11	8,361
No panel participation	4,946	3,415

Data: DEAS 2014-2023

Table 2. Cross-sectional samples

Panel wave	Cases
2014	6,424
2017	2,960
2021	2,645

2023

2,179

Data: DEAS 2014-2023

Table 3. Longitudinal samples

	Cases	Observations
trajectory 1 (NU to U)	3,249	9,175
trajectory 2 (U to NU)	3,107	8,705

Note: The samples contain trajectories with the respective transition and additionally all trajectories without a transition (see Data); NU = non-usage, U= usage; Data: DEAS 2014-2023

Table 4. Cross-sectional descriptives (only for all purposes)

	2014			2017			2021			2023		
	NU	OU	FU	NU	OU	FU	NU	OU	FU	NU	OU	FU
Frequency	2,118	959	3,387	1,007	392	1,575	561	239	1,853	396	201	1,984
Share	32.8	14.8	52.4	33.9	13.2	53.0	21.1	9.0	69.8	15.3	7.8	76.9
Women ¹ (share in %)	54.8	58.1	46.5	54.8	52.8	39.4	55.4	44.4	45.6	58.1	43.3	47.8
Ever employed ² (share in %)	99.6	99.8	99.7	99.7	99.7	99.9	99.6	99.6	99.8	99.2	100	99.8
Grandparents ³ (share in %)	75.4	54.4	42.0	78.8	74.2	72.8	79.9	74.4	71.2	77.7	75.3	72.5
Parents ⁴ (share in %)	88.2	88.0	86.1	88.5	89.3	88.3	89.8	86.2	88.8	88.1	87.1	89.6
No vocational qualification (share in %)	17.4	6.0	5.4	13.1	3.3	5.5	13.0	6.7	4.3	14.9	6.5	4.2
Vocational qualification (dual system) (share in %)	47.4	44.4	32.5	45.9	37.8	27.0	42.1	43.1	27.8	39.5	44.3	28.5
School-based vocational qualification (share in %)	11.2	12.9	9.4	12.2	14.0	9.3	12.8	8.4	10.1	11.5	8.6	9.6
Trade / Technical school degree (share in %)	12.1	18.0	14.8	13.5	15.3	15.2	15.3	9.6	14.8	15.2	10.8	14.9
University degree (including Applied Sciences) (share in %)	11.9	18.6	37.8	15.3	29.6	43.0	16.8	32.2	43.0	18.9	29.7	42.9
Age (mean)	72.9	62.0	60.2	77.1	73.0	72.4	79.2	74.3	73.2	80.4	76.0	73.8
Network size (mean)	4.5	5.4	5.5	4.4	5.4	5.4	3.7	4.2	4.6	3.9	4.7	5.0
Subjective health (mean)	3.1	3.2	3.2	3.1	3.2	3.2	3.1	3.3	3.2	3.0	3.2	3.2

Notes: NU = Non-usage, OU = Occasional usage, FU = Frequent usage; Reference categories: ¹ men, ² never employed, ³ no grandparents, ⁴ no parents; Data: DEAS 2014-2023

Table 5. Internet usage over time for all purposes

	2014	2017	2021	2023
lifelong learning	0.121***	0.197***	0.201***	0.070
gatherings	0.028	0.077*	0.097	0.222**
walk	0.003	-0.010	0.013	-0.067
sport	0.060***	0.002	-0.050	0.114
artistically active	0.035*	0.074	0.089*	-0.195*
culturally active	0.128***	0.186**	0.253**	0.456**
sporting event	-0.031	0.076	-0.198**	-0.211

board games	-0.030	0.077	0.178**	0.056
courses	0.091***	0.088	0.070	0.065
stable group	0.012	0.034	0.127*	-0.135
higher vocational education	0.104***	0.091***	0.053	0.142***
women	-0.195***	-0.255***	-0.274***	-0.163
ever participated in labor market	-0.110	0.113	-0.461	-0.048
chronological age	-0.027***	-0.034***	-0.038***	-0.038**
existence of grandchildren	-0.138***	-0.016	-0.074	0.174
existence of children	0.143***	-0.084	0.089	0.032
network size	0.006	0.017	0.013	-0.008
better subjective health	-0.002	0.042	0.034	0.090
Constant	2.861***	2.728***	3.843***	3.831**
Observations	6,424	2,960	2,645	2,179
R-squared	0.418	0.313	0.363	0.421

Note: * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001; Data: DEAS 2014-2023

Table 6. Internet usage over time for social purposes

	2014	2017	2021	2023
service purposes	0.151***	0.175***	0.174**	0.096*
informal learning purposes	0.608***	0.612***	0.633***	0.763***
lifelong learning	-0.011	0.032	0.050	-0.000
gatherings	0.019	0.030	0.064	0.088
walk	0.024	-0.031	-0.032	-0.143
sport	0.022	0.010	0.045	0.109*
artistically active	0.036**	0.009	0.023	-0.044
culturally active	0.012	0.057	-0.032	0.342***
sporting event	0.032	0.083*	-0.001	-0.028
board games	-0.009	0.024	-0.015	0.050
courses	0.049**	0.052	0.021	-0.042
stable group	0.024	-0.002	0.071*	0.011
higher vocational education	0.016*	-0.002	0.049*	-0.021
women	0.064**	0.060	0.143**	0.180***
ever participated in labor market	-0.108	-0.126	-0.089	-0.099
chronological age	-0.001	-0.007**	-0.005	0.002
existence of grandchildren	-0.073**	0.076	-0.044	0.186*
existence of children	0.044	-0.069	0.247*	-0.017
network size	0.011**	0.018**	0.015	-0.003
better subjective health	-0.012	-0.017	-0.012	0.010
Constant	0.110	0.550	0.050	-0.411
Observations	6,424	2,960	2,645	2,179
R-squared	0.605	0.666	0.693	0.777

Note: * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001; Data: DEAS 2014-2023

Table 7. Internet usage over time for service purposes

	2014	2017	2021	2023
informal learning purposes	0.364***	0.272***	0.315***	0.325***

social purposes	0.132***	0.184***	0.205***	0.115
lifelong learning	0.037**	0.051**	0.094**	0.205***
gatherings	-0.005	-0.006	-0.064	0.048
walk	-0.011	-0.007	0.024	0.067
sport	-0.004	0.004	-0.002	-0.010
artistically active	-0.023	-0.021	-0.001	0.030
culturally active	0.018	0.027	-0.016	-0.140*
sporting event	0.009	0.010	-0.063	-0.028
board games	0.002	-0.026	-0.008	0.063
courses	0.026	0.027	0.153**	0.090
stable group	-0.000	-0.012	0.077**	-0.008
higher vocational education	0.030***	0.025	-0.004	0.057**
women	-0.110***	-0.210***	-0.290***	-0.284***
ever participated in labor market	-0.196*	0.213	0.132	0.044
chronological age	-0.009***	-0.012***	-0.013**	-0.002
existence of grandchildren	-0.008	-0.001	0.125	-0.182
existence of children	0.068*	0.047	-0.090	0.215
network size	0.004	-0.001	0.005	-0.001
better subjective health	0.007	0.015	-0.006	0.036
Constant	1.167***	1.149***	1.162**	-0.168
Observations	6,424	2,961	2,645	2,179
R-squared	0.522	0.477	0.528	0.581

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$; Data: DEAS 2014-2023

Table 8. Internet usage over time for informal learning purposes

	2014	2017	2021	2023
social purposes	0.482***	0.643***	0.596***	0.672***
service purposes	0.328***	0.272***	0.252***	0.240***
lifelong learning	0.058***	0.045*	0.035	-0.021
gatherings	-0.004	0.008	0.021	-0.016
walk	-0.008	0.026	0.044	0.098
sport	0.020*	-0.003	-0.054	-0.060
artistically active	0.008	0.037	0.024	-0.051
culturally active	0.048*	0.016	0.156*	-0.120*
sporting event	-0.033*	-0.038	-0.065	-0.035
board games	-0.004	0.011	0.084	-0.056
courses	0.015	-0.007	-0.031	0.033
stable group	-0.007	0.025	-0.026	-0.052
higher vocational education	0.035***	0.033*	-0.018	0.058**
women	-0.101***	-0.095*	-0.131**	-0.138**
ever participated in labor market	0.080	0.052	-0.237	0.070
chronological age	-0.010***	-0.004	-0.009*	-0.019*
existence of grandchildren	-0.024	-0.078	-0.075	-0.010
existence of children	0.011	0.007	-0.084	-0.075
network size	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.000
better subjective health	0.001	0.023	0.028	0.002
Constant	0.919***	0.321	1.268***	2.197**

Observations	6,424	2,960	2,645	2,179
R-squared	0.695	0.682	0.715	0.803

Note: * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001; Data: DEAS 2014-2023

Table 9. Longitudinal descriptives

	Transition into usage	Transition non-usage	into Stable Usage	Stable Usage	Non-Usage
Frequency	247		104	2,195	812
Share	7.4		3.1	65.4	24.2
Women ¹ (share in %)	59.5		55.8	42.7	54.9
Grandparents ² (share in %)					
2014	80.7		69.6	71.2	79.5
2017	79.4		73.6	72.4	80.1
2021	78.0		74.3	72.4	80.5
2023	80.8		78.3	74.0	79.3
Parents ³ (share in %)					
2014	91.1		87.1	89.8	90.3
2017	90.7		86.2	88.5	89.7
2021	88.3		87.1	89.3	90.5
2023	90.4		90.0	89.6	89.5
No vocational qualification (share in %)	10.1		11.5	4.2	14.2
Vocational qualification (dual system) (share in %)	44.5		35.6	28.2	45.2
School-based vocational qualification (share in %)	15.4		11.5	9.4	12.4
Trade / Technical school degree (share in %)	13.8		16.3	15.2	13.5
University degree (including Applied Sciences) (share in %)	16.2		25.0	43.0	14.7
Age (mean)					
2014	72.9		74.0	71.3	75.2
2017	75.0		76.3	72.5	77.9
2021	77.6		78.9	73.3	80.1
2023	79.4		80.6	75.1	81.2
Network size (mean)					
2014	4.8		5.1	5.5	4.5
2017	4.7		4.9	5.5	4.3
2021	3.9		4.0	4.6	3.7
2023	4.3		4.0	4.9	3.9
Subjective health (mean)					
2014	3.2		3.3	3.3	3.3
2017	3.1		3.2	3.3	3.1
2021	3.2		3.2	3.3	3.1
2023	3.1		3.1	3.3	3.0

Notes: Reference categories: ¹ men, ² no grandparents, ³ no parents; Data: DEAS 2014-2023

Table 10. The likelihood of the transition into and out of internet usage, longitudinal results (AMEs)

	trajectory 1 (NU to U)	trajectory 2 (U to NU)
Between- Effects		
lifelong learning	0.117***	0.128***
gatherings	0.027***	0.033***
walk	0.023**	0.033***
sport	0.039***	0.048***
artistically active	0.005	0.012
culturally active	0.085***	0.113***
sporting event	-0.020*	-0.044***
board games	0.025**	0.031**
courses	0.044***	0.039*
stable group	-0.001	-0.002
women	-0.099***	-0.105***
higher vocational education	0.043***	0.044***
existence of grandchildren	-0.032**	-0.039*
existence of children	0.046**	0.056**
network size	0.014***	0.011***
better subjective health	-0.000	0.002
chronological age	-0.016***	-0.019***
Within-Effects		
lifelong learning	0.013**	0.007
gatherings	0.003	0.006
walk	0.001	0.002
sport	0.004	-0.002
artistically active	-0.004	-0.001
culturally active	0.010	0.001
sporting event	0.005	0.007
board games	0.001	-0.002
courses	-0.003	0.010
stable group	-0.000	0.003
existence of grandchildren	-0.036*	-0.015
existence of children	0.038	-0.039
network size	0.001	0.001
better subjective health	0.003	0.001
Cases	3250	3108
Observations	9175	8705

Note: * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001, NU = non-usage, U= usage; Data: DEAS 2014-2023

